

AN ONGOING CONVERSATION ON DIGITAL ARCHITECTURAL HERITAGE: INSIGHTS FROM FOCUS GROUPS IN AOTEAROA NEW ZEALAND

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Heritage preservation in Aotearoa, New Zealand, is becoming increasingly vulnerable due to the growing impacts of natural and human-induced disasters often attributed to climate change. Despite mounting risks and irreversible losses, progress in addressing these challenges has been limited. This research draws on insights from three focus group discussions held as part of the ongoing project Digitalisation of Heritage in New Zealand, involving 16 professionals from industry, academia, community, and government sectors. The discussions explored the role of digital technologies in the documentation and preservation of built architectural heritage. Participants reflected on the opportunities and limitations of using digital tools, the challenge of storing data, maintaining authenticity in digital representations, and the value of integrating digital practices into heritage workflows. The findings underscore the potential of digitalisation not only as a method for preservation but also as a means of celebrating and safeguarding heritage for future generations. This paper contributes to ongoing discourse in the field, offering practical recommendations and inviting further dialogue with digital practitioners to refine and strengthen data collection approaches to heritage conservation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Digital preservation is increasingly central to the documentation and protection of historical and cultural heritage, offering advanced methods for recording, visualising, and sharing built environments [1], [2], [3]. Within architectural

heritage, digital tools—such as photogrammetry, LiDAR, and Building Information Modelling (BIM) are being used internationally to support conservation efforts[4]. However, in Aotearoa New Zealand, the widespread integration of these tools into standard conservation workflows remains limited due to a combination of cultural, institutional, and technical barriers [5].

This short paper draws on research conducted by the Digital Heritage Research Centre (DHRC), [6] which explored professional perspectives on digital tools' current and future role in heritage practice. Building on a national survey including 156 participants across industry, academia, government, and iwi-linked organisations, the project identified key challenges and opportunities for digital conservation in New Zealand's built heritage sector. The findings were summarised and published as three core themes: [1] Current use and associated challenges, [2] Interdisciplinary engagement and knowledge-sharing, [3] Barriers to standard integration into conservation workflows.

These themes were further developed through a series of focus group discussions with interested survey participants over three days. Each day consisted of one focus group that was dependent on the availability of the participants and was split into three sessions: [1] Discussing the challenges and benefits of digitalisation based on their experience, [2] participants' engagement with others during digitalisation, and [3] discussing the future use of these tools as mainstream use for Aotearoa. Each

focus group consisted of at least one member from each stakeholder group: community, government, industry and academia, which proved immensely beneficial for discussing downfalls attributed to one another in the survey study.

To ensure consistency in data analysis across the survey and focus groups, transcripts from each session were examined using Braun and Clarke’s thematic analysis method. This method involved familiarisation with the data from each focus group session, followed by systematic coding and thematic mapping. Transcripts were reviewed side by side and individually, enabling the identification of recurring patterns and key themes.

II. FINDINGS

Upon initial analysis, the survey studies highlighted broad concerns and proposals regarding the digitalisation of heritage, while the focus groups offered a further exploration of these themes, as shown in Figure 1. Discussions primarily surrounding the use of digital tools, challenges encountered during information sharing, and difficulties integrating these tools into standard workflows. While the discussions shed light on key barriers—such as lack of funding, inadequate training, and the perceived complexity of operating the tools—there was little discourse on overcoming these challenges. Instead, the participants revealed a strong desire for

practical frameworks and culturally inclusive methodologies that respond to Aotearoa’s context.

Although the findings are still preliminary, the initial coding of data from the three focus groups revealed several key themes:

- 1) **Digital downsides:** High costs, interpretation challenges, limited expertise, and accessibility barriers to using the necessary software and hardware.
- 2) **Management:** Widespread uncertainty about responsibility for managing heritage assets, particularly given that many sites are government-owned.
- 3) **Education and awareness:** The need to improve client understanding, public appreciation, education initiatives, and opportunities for sharing expertise.

Survey results revealed significant challenges in the operation, interpretation and accessibility of digital tools, with insufficient training and expertise highlighted as key. These limitations contributed to what one participant described as heritage “falling through the gaps.” Focus group discussions further unpacked these issues, highlighting three interconnected themes: first, the considerable digital challenges posed by high costs, interpretation difficulties, limited expertise, and accessibility barriers associated with specialised software and hardware; second, persistent management

FOCUS GROUP ANALYSIS

Figure 1: Preliminary analysis on one focus group representing themes and codes over the 3 sessions [illustrated by Iman Khan].

uncertainties, with participants noting widespread misunderstandings over who holds responsibility for safeguarding heritage assets. Although many significant sites are owned by government entities, participants strongly emphasised that the duty to define and regulate management practices should remain a governmental responsibility, regardless of ownership structure; and third, a pervasive lack of education and awareness, particularly among clients, the wider public, and professionals, which participants identified as a critical barrier to effective heritage and digital preservation.

III. CONCLUSION

This paper aims to address the unique preservation challenges of Aotearoa New Zealand by fostering dialogue with iPRES attendees. It extends an invitation to digital preservation professionals—including built environment practitioners, academics, industry stakeholders, government representatives, policymakers, community members, and others interested in interdisciplinary, practice-led approaches—to contribute insights from their respective contexts. Through these shared perspectives, the paper seeks to build a collective understanding of effective digital heritage integration, encompassing technical, social, and ethical considerations.

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